

Attitudes of the Faculty Members in the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait towards the Experience of Distance Learning During the Corona Pandemic

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 10, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 22, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Distance, Learning, Corona Pandemic</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5233904</p>	<p><i>This study aimed to identify the attitudes of faculty members in the colleges of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait towards distance Learning experience, which was activated during the Corona pandemic. To achieve the research objectives; a questionnaire was used. A sample of 185 faculty members were selected, the descriptive-analytical approach was adopted, the results indicated that the attitudes of the faculty members towards The distance learning experience were positive, moreover results indicated that there were no apparent differences between the arithmetic means of the attitudes towards distance learning due to the gender variable. On the other hand; The results showed that there were statistically significant differences according to the college variable; Experience variable and academic Degree variable. The researchers presented a set of recommendations, which revolve in their entirety about evaluating the experience of distance learning from several perspectives and destinations, to further ensure its effectiveness based on the attitudes of its users.</i></p>

Introduction

At the end of 2019, the world was affected by a global crisis that fundamentally changed the normal way of life, which is the COVID-19 pandemic. At the beginning of the year 2020, the crisis worsened and caused the almost complete closure of educational institutions, transportation and the global economy, and the closure of shops and companies in various parts of the world.

And the world began to develop alternative plans in almost desperate attempts to address this pandemic and save the economy and education from collapse, most countries of the world have recommended the adoption of distance education to reduce the interruption of education and avoid negative effects if the crisis continues, Countries followed a general system of quarantine, which put the education system in front of huge challenges between the opening and closing of schools, the quality of education and the ability of teachers and learners to adapt to unprecedented situations (Alturise, 2020).

For this reason, educational administrations have adopted the E-Learning Management System (LMS), which is a program designed to help create an interactive learning environment, control the management of academic content, and follow up and evaluate learning outcomes. Distance education relied on technological means, communications, and the Internet through the use of educational platforms and applications. Distance education came to represent the only solution in light of the disruption and paralysis of state agencies in dealing with the issue of the pandemic and its repercussions at all levels, including the readiness of the educational system and the possibilities available to deal with the pandemic by teachers and learners (Bataineh, Atoum, Alsmadi, Shikhali, 2020).

The shock of school closures caused huge losses in education and increased dropout rates among students. More than 1.6 billion students (which constitute more than 94% of students worldwide) have been affected in more than 190 countries and on all continents (UNESCO, 2020). Therefore, many countries have taken the only option in education in light of this pandemic, which is "distance education" to ensure the safety of students, teachers and their families (Dhawan, 2020)

Statement of study problem

There is no doubt that any new experiment or initiative in any field, including the educational field, needs evaluation and diagnosis to address the pros and cons of the experiment, to ensure its success and continuity through correcting errors - if any - and avoiding them in the future, in addition to strengthening and maintaining its positives. And since the experience of distance education in higher education institutions in the State of Kuwait is a relatively new experience, not to mention that it came suddenly, in which it was necessary to deal with technology and electronic programs in teaching, to deal with the exceptional circumstances experienced by the country and the Ministry of Education in particular. the preparations for implementing the distance education experience came very quickly by training faculty members and students on the use of electronic

programs and applications in a short time, so it was necessary to conduct an evaluation of that experience and to obtain the feedback emanating from the executive authorities, including the faculty members, as in the current study, and to obtain on their notes. Information about the degree of benefit from that experience is still scarce, and the degree of satisfaction of its implementers and beneficiaries did not have time to verify it. Therefore, this study came in response to this demand and scientifically proven it by collecting data from faculty members working in the faculties of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training and identifying their views about the distance education experience identify their observations through which we can discern their acceptance of that experience, which will be considered as an indicator to the degree of its success in light of the difficult circumstances that the country is experiencing as a result of the Corona pandemic.

Study questions

What are the attitudes of faculty members towards the distance Learning experience in the colleges of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait?

Do faculty members' attitudes towards the distance Learning experience in the colleges of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait differ according the variable (gender, college, degree, years of experience) ?

The importance of the study:

This study seeks to identify the attitudes of faculty members in the faculties of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Teaching about the distance education experience. Through the result of this study, we will be able to obtain the necessary information that will be benefited from, especially by officials and decision-makers from those in charge of distance education to develop this new experience, as well as making the necessary adjustments required according to the result of this study. The importance of this study also lies in the fact that it provides those in charge of the educational process and those interested in educational affairs with a clear picture of the extent to which students' academic achievement has changed, negatively or positively, by changing teaching methods and means from face-to-face education to using technology and electronic programs by looking at the views of faculty members. In general, this study indicates the extent to which faculty members accept the distance education experience, especially for those who have no inclination towards using technology in teaching, or their academic disciplines and academic decisions may not require the use of technology.

The limits of the study:

Spatial boundaries: the colleges affiliated to the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait.

Time limits: the first semester of the academic years 2020/2021.

Subject Limits: The study was limited to knowing the attitudes of faculty members in the State of Kuwait about the experience of distance education during the Corona pandemic.

Human limits: The study was limited to all faculty members working in colleges affiliated with the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training.

Study Methodology:

the descriptive approach was adopted in the current study.

Terminology of study:

Distance education:

An organizational and emerging process that satisfies the needs of learners through their interaction with the educational experiences provided to them in unconventional ways that depend on their ability, through the use of multimedia technology without being restricted to a specific time or place and without directly relying on the teacher (Alnasraween, Ammari, Alsoudi, Alkursheh, Almahameed, 2021).

As for another definition, it is "a system that allows the possibility of transferring and communicating the scientific material through multiple means without the need for the student to come to the classroom regularly, as the student is responsible for educating himself" (Al-Zahi, 2012:59).

TeamsPlatform:

It is a communications and business platform owned by Microsoft and is part of Microsoft 365 programs. Teams started in 2016 to organize high-quality electronic communication between individuals. The program serves distance education, chatting, messaging, interactive live work space, live video conferencing, and interactive storage and file storage for teachers and learners (Warren, 2016).

Model system:

Moodle was developed as an e-learning tool by creating a virtual learning environment by Martin Dougiamas in August 2002 to help teachers create online courses and educational programs with an emphasis on interactive and collaborative learning with learners. The development of the program has continued to this day as an effective learning platform used to transfer data (Jordan, 2013).

Study Population and Sample:

The study population consists of all members of the teaching staff working in the colleges of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training, who is (1398), distributed over five colleges (College of Basic

Education, College of Technology Studies, College of Business Studies, College of Health Sciences, College of Nursing). The available sample method was used in selecting the study members, which consisted of (185) faculty members working in the colleges of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training.

Study tool:

The researchers designed a closed questionnaire that consisted of (38) statements distributed on (4) domains distributed as follows:

The first domain: the opinion of the faculty member on the quality of the training programs and technical support provided by the educational institution

(Teams) The second domain: the opinion of the faculty member on the use of the program

The third domain: the opinion of the faculty member on teaching methods through distance learning.

The fourth domain: the opinion of the faculty member in evaluating students through distance learning

Tool Validity

The content validity was extracted by presenting it to a group of experienced and specialized members of the faculty in the college to express their opinions in terms of the suitability and clarity of the wording, the integrity of the language, the extent to which the paragraphs belong to the measured behaviour, and the extent to which the alternatives belong to the paragraph and deleting, adding or modifying what they deem appropriate, and in light of the arbitrators' notes and opinions, the required amendments have been made.

Tool Reliability:

The stability of the internal consistency was extracted through the Cronbach's alpha equation, where the study tool was applied to an exploratory sample from outside the main study sample whose number was (30) faculty members, and table (1) shows these values.

Table(1)
The Values of Cronbach alpha for internal consistency

No	Domain	Cronbach Alpha
1	The quality of the training programs and technical support provided by the educational institution	0.85
2	Using Teams	0.78
3	Teaching methods through distance learning	0.83
4	Student assessment through distance learning	0.82
	Total Degree	0.86

It is noted from the results of Table (1) that the stability values of the internal consistency method Cronbach's alpha were all suitable for the current study, as they reached for the total score (0.86) and ranged for dimensions between (0.78) and (0.85)

Correction of the study tool

To judge the arithmetic averages of the study tool, the equation was used: (the highest value in the grading - the lowest value in the grading) / number of categories

$$1.33 = \frac{3}{(1-5)}$$

:Thus, the arithmetic averages are judged as follows

Low (2.33 - 1)

Medium (3.67 - 2.34)

.is high (5 - 3.68)

Theoretical framework:

The origins of distance learning :

The origin of distance education dates back more than 200 years, beginning in 1729 by Caleb Philips, who did weekly lessons through the Boston Gazette. Subsequently, the radio was used for the same purpose in 1922, when the University of Pennsylvania of America presented some courses over the radio. With the development of the media, television was used in 1968 by engineering students at Stanford University in America. After the entry of computers into the educational field in 1982, and the Internet in 1992, this helped spread closed learning management systems in 1999. MIT launched Open Courses Systems, which was used by more than 65 million people in 2002. And then Khan Academy in 2008, which is used by more than 71 million people around the world (Almomani, Alnasraween, Almosa,2020).

The Concept Of Distance Education:

The concept of distance education is defined as a new means of acquiring scientific knowledge that emerged as a result of the rapid development in contemporary technology so that it is done by separating the teacher and the learner in the normal educational environment and creating another environment that separates geographically

between each of them in order to overcome the conditions that prevent students from acquiring knowledge in the traditional way (Byun & Slavin, 2020).

E-learning depends on the use of modern communication mechanisms such as computers, networks, and multimedia, such as sound, image, graphics, search mechanisms, electronic libraries, as well as Internet portals in receiving information, acquiring skills, and interaction between the student and the teacher and between the student and the school – and perhaps between the school and the teacher – nor “This type of education requires the presence of school buildings or classrooms and even eliminates all physical components of education” moreover distance education is the provision of scientific material through all available electronic means in the education process, whether it is via the Internet, or an electronic means such as a computer and its networks, or a mobile phone and others (Almomani, Alnasraween, Almosa, 2020).

To apply this type of education, distance education has characteristics or requirements that help in its application, including the necessity of separating the teacher and the learner, as well as finding technological media between the teacher and the learner to ensure transmission and reception between them, in addition to the fact that the learner bears the responsibility to absorb and absorb the materials Academic courses (Shahmoradi, Changizi, Mehraeen, Bashiri, Jannat & Hosseini, 2018).

Distance education goals:

Any new educational style that is different from the traditional one must have goals and meaning from its use. Nor is the ultimate goal to ensure that students acquire the necessary knowledge and skills that prepare them academically for their future profession. Note that some of these skills may only be obtained through this new educational style. Therefore, distance education has specific goals, as it did not come from a vacuum, considering that it necessitated the transfer of the student from a normal, traditional educational environment that has been applied for centuries to a new environment that is different and isolated - somewhat - geographically from that normal environment that includes the teaching and administrative staff in the educational institution to which the students belong. Therefore, when using this new teaching style, it was necessary to have justifications for its use that can be reached by recognizing the goals of distance education, which are summarized by Hinnawi & Najm (2019) thus:

- Development of community members culturally and scientifically.
- Addressing the problem of lack of teaching staff.
- Addressing the problem of the lack of financial resources allocated to the educational process.
- Providing new methods as a kind of concern for equal educational opportunities among members of society.
- Diversification of future job opportunities when current conditions prevent a commitment to regular education.

The importance of distance education

Al-Qahtani (2010) indicated that the importance of distance education lies in the fulfilment of needs, including:

- Contribute to the eradication of illiteracy and the education of adults and girls in the Arab world.
- Meeting the needs of society from the increasing demand for education.
- Activating community service in the field of training and education.
- The population increase and the attendant increase in the number of learners and the desire for a plurality of study methods.
- Following up the professional movement in the community in the development, and training of employees.
- Saving time, effort and spending on traditional education.
- Keeping abreast of confidential development in technology, means of communication, and new continuous technologies

Advantages of Distance Learning

The benefits of distance learning are as follows:

- Low material cost: Web lessons are less expensive for students, teachers, and educational institutions, and through them, books, curricula and notes can be dispensed with.
- Electronic publishing: The Internet provides an easier mechanism for electronic publishing, as it enables students and teachers to compose and publish their work in various parts of the world.
- Multiple experiences: due to the abundance of information on the Internet from experts, authors and innovators, which adds a variety of different sources of knowledge and expertise.
- Saving effort and time: The student can obtain information from its sources within a few seconds, thus saving transportation from the educational institution, home and library.
- Diversification of teaching methods: enables the student to receive the scientific material in different ways suitable for him, whether read, audio or visual.
- Continuing to access the curricula: the student can obtain the information he wants at the time that suits him, within 24 hours a day (Alnasraween, Almousa, Almomani, & Ammari, 2020).

Among the benefits that distance education achieves in the educational process, as stated in some studies, are the following:

- Increasing the possibility of communication and communication between the parties to the educational process, including students and professors, and the exchange of opinions and points of view.
- Saving time, cost, and ease of developing electronic programs and modifying their content.
- The ability to provide effective electronic curricula, authoring and technically coordinating them.
- Easy for parents to follow up on students through communication channels.
- A major source of information and knowledge available to learners at all times.
- Assisting in dialogue and discussion between students and teachers, which helps to enrich the educational process and strengthen the motivation to learn.
- Increasing the courage and freedom that students lack in traditional classes.
- Helping students to become self-reliant and to promote self-learning.
- Flexibility in time and place around the clock.
- Easy access to the teacher and communication with him outside the main working hours.
- Providing all types of assessment, subjective and summative, and provides immediate feedback to learners.
- The possibility of reaching large numbers of learners in various parts of the world.
- Diversity of teaching methods and sources. (Al-Mazahra, 2014; Al-Zain, 2016).

Disadvantages of Distance Learning:

Through the use of the electronic program, we can summarize some of its disadvantages as follows:

- In general, many exams in e-learning are limited to direct objective questions.
- E-learning reduces the role of the teacher as the main influence in the educational activity of the learner.
- The possibility of hacking the electronic system and sometimes losing privacy.
- The absence of the role of the educational institution and the positive presence of it as an influencing factor in the social upbringing of individuals (Ammari, 2020).

Obstacles Facing Distance Learning

Al-Massad(2020) clarified some of the obstacles to distance Learning, which were summarized as follows:

- The difference in abilities and capabilities of teachers in explaining and managing the lesson.
- The inability of all financial students to obtain modern devices such as laptops or tablets and other devices needed in distance Learning.
- Scarcity of digital resources and educational applications directed to learners with special needs.
- Severe and continuous pressure on communications networks and the internet at the same time, which weakens the quality of communication.
- The absence of psychological counselling and guidance that the student receives in the educational institution in case of need.
- The existence of some learners' difficulty in managing time compared to the traditional education specified in time and place to complete academic duties and responsibilities.
- The inability of evaluation mechanisms to control cheating and rely on the integrity of the learner during assignments and tests.
- Dismissing a large number of teachers in the event of the transition to distance Learning.
- Inequality in educational systems, with low-income children suffering more than their middle- and high-income peers in the availability of devices and access to the Internet around the clock.

Previous Studies:

Al-Zahrani (2020) conducted a study in which it sought to monitor the attitudes of the faculty members working at Umm Al-Qura University towards the use of e-learning "Blackboard" in education. The study was applied to a sample of 90 faculty members. The results of the study indicated that the study sample's attitudes were positive towards e-learning in education, which includes the Blackboard platform. The results of the study also indicated that there were no differences in the trends of the study sample due to each of the sex variables; Specialization; Scientific rank.

Also, Al-Buhairi (2019) conducted a study aimed at revealing the attitudes of faculty members towards the use of electronic platforms in university teaching, as well as to reveal the difficulties facing their application in teaching. The researcher applied a questionnaire to a sample of 40 faculty members working in several universities (Menoufia, Tanta, Mansoura and Benha). The results of the study revealed that faculty members have high tendencies towards the use of electronic platforms in university teaching. The study also revealed several difficulties are facing the application of electronic platforms in teaching. The researcher recommended the necessity of applying electronic platforms in university education and removing all obstacles that prevent this.

Al-Shuaibt (2019) conducted a study aimed at identifying the attitudes of the faculty members at Shobak University College towards the application of educational technology in the college. The researcher used a questionnaire to reveal the attitudes of the faculty members towards the application of educational technology. The questionnaire was applied to a sample of 27 faculty members. The results of the study revealed that the

attitudes of the study sample towards the application of educational technology in the college were positive and to a high degree. The results revealed that there were no statistically significant differences between the responses of the study sample due to the gender variable; Years of experience and learning method.

Al-Shehri (2019) also conducted a study aimed at identifying the attitudes of faculty members towards the use of e-learning in teaching mathematics courses at King Khalid University. The researcher used a questionnaire to collect data from a sample of 42 members of the teaching staff working in the Mathematics Department at King Khalid University. The results revealed a discrepancy in the attitudes of the study sample towards e-learning in teaching mathematics courses, ranging between high and medium. The results also revealed that there were no statistically significant differences between the answers of the study sample according to the variables of gender and nationality. While the results indicated that there were statistically significant differences between the trends of the study sample due to the variable number of years of experience and academic rank.

The study of Hinnawi and Najm (2019) aimed to identify the degree of readiness of primary school teachers in public schools in Nablus District to employ e-learning by researching the degree of their attitudes towards e-learning, the level of their competencies in using it, and the degree of obstacles to its application from their point of view. The study used the descriptive analytical method, and the study tool consisted of a questionnaire, which included 40 items in the field of competencies, the field of attitudes, and the field of obstacles, and it was distributed to all members of the sample, which numbered 120 male and female teachers, who were randomly selected from the study population of teachers in the Nablus District. The results of the study revealed that the degree of the three domains (competencies, attitudes, and obstacles) was high. There are statistically significant differences in the field of competencies due to the variables of age, the rate of daily use of the Internet, and the number of courses in the field of information technology. There is a direct relationship between the level of competencies and the degree of teachers' attitudes towards employing it, while there was a negative relationship with a statistical significance between the degree of obstacles to the employment of e-learning from the teachers' point of view and the degree of their attitudes towards this employment.

Al-Saeedi (2016) conducted a study aimed at identifying the attitudes of the faculty members at Majmaah University towards e-learning and its employment in university education, in addition to revealing the differences between the study sample according to the variable of training programs and years of experience. The researcher used a questionnaire to collect data from a sample of 197 faculty members working at Majmaah University. The results indicated that the study sample's attitudes towards e-learning were positive and to a high degree. The results also indicated that there were statistically significant differences between the study sample due to the variable of training programs and the number of years of experience.

Kisanga (2016) conducted a study in which he sought to identify the attitudes of faculty members working in higher education institutions in Tanzania towards e-learning. The researcher used a questionnaire that was applied to 258 members of the teaching staff working in four institutions of higher education. The results of the study showed that faculty members working in higher education institutions in Tanzania have positive attitudes towards e-learning. The study concluded that it is necessary to train faculty members in higher education institutions on e-learning. Also, the study recommended the need to support the factors that create positive attitudes among faculty members in higher education institutions in Tanzania.

Al-Humairi's study (2014) revealed the trends of the educational community in the Tabuk region towards the use of e-learning and its relationship to some variables. The researcher used the measure of the educational community's tendency towards the application of e-learning on a random sample of students of higher education and general education, teachers of public education and faculty members at the University of Tabuk, consisting of (13025) individuals. The results of the study revealed that the attitudes of the educational community in the Tabuk region were high to a positive degree, and the results did not show statistically significant differences in the attitudes of male and female teachers due to the type and educational stage in which they work.

Al-Qahtani (2010) conducted a study To identify the views of faculty members towards the use of virtual classrooms, in addition to the obstacles they may face in distance education programs at King Abdulaziz University in Jeddah. The researcher used the descriptive approach and prepared a questionnaire addressed to the faculty members to identify their views. The study sample consisted of 120 faculty members at King Abdulaziz University. The results of the study resulted in the acceptance of faculty members in general towards the use of virtual classrooms in distance education programs. The study also showed that there were statistically significant differences towards the use of virtual classrooms in distance education programs and the degree of familiarity with using computers, while there were no statistically significant differences in the rest of the variables of the study that included the type of college, years of service and the degree of familiarity with the use of the Internet.

Muhammad (2013) conducted a study that aimed to identify the attitudes of faculty members working at the Faculty of Education at Hantoub University towards the application of e-learning methods and techniques and their relationship to the gender variable; Academic rank and number of years of experience. The researcher designed a questionnaire that was applied to a sample of 43 faculty members. The results showed that the attitudes of faculty members towards the application of e-learning methods and techniques were positive. The

results also showed that there were no statistically significant differences between the trends of the sample members due to the gender variable; Academic rank and number of years of experience.

Al-Osaili study (2012) aimed to reveal the reality of e-learning and its challenges at Al-Quds Open University in the Hebron Educational District, and from the academic supervisors' point of view. The researcher followed the descriptive approach, and the study sample consisted of 80 supervisors who used or were trained on the e-learning system at the university. The researcher used a questionnaire to collect data. The results of the study revealed that the responses of academic supervisors about the reality of e-learning were high. The study showed that there were no statistically significant differences in the variables of the study program, years of experience and the nature of the supervisor's work at the university. It also showed statistically significant differences in the skills of using virtual classrooms by academic supervisors.

Al-Shammari (2012) conducted a study aimed at revealing the attitudes of mathematics teachers in the intermediate stage towards the use of e-learning in teaching. The researcher adopted the descriptive approach by using a questionnaire on a sample of 147 teachers in the Hail region. The results of the study revealed a medium degree of attitudes towards the use of e-learning in teaching mathematics. It also showed statistically significant differences between the averages of teachers' attitudes due to the variables of academic qualification and in favor of graduate studies, and years of experience in favor of from 5 years to less than 10 years.

In another study, Krishnakumar & Rajesh (2011) conducted a study to identify the attitudes of higher education faculty and staff in Tamil Nadu state towards e-learning. The number of the study sample was 225 faculty members, who were chosen in an intentional way. The researchers used a questionnaire to measure the attitudes of faculty members towards e-learning. The results of the study showed that faculty members have positive attitudes towards e-learning. The results also showed that there were statistically significant differences between faculty members due to experience in computers and information and communication technology in favor of those who have experience in that.

Commenting on Previous Studies

It is clear by examining the previous studies that examined the trends of distance learning and e-learning in general, that in their entirety they indicated that the trends were positive. This result indicates that there is awareness among the members of the samples in those studies towards the necessity of employing technology in teaching in line with the development taking place in teaching methods to facilitate the process of communicating information. Also the majority of previous studies adopted the descriptive approach in conducting them, and that the most widely used tool is the questionnaire. Several studies have also shown the importance of the experience variable in using technology and virtual classrooms.

Results and Discussion

The results of the first study, which states: What are the attitudes of faculty members towards the distance learning experience in the colleges of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait?

To answer this question, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the faculty members' attitudes to the distance learning experience in the faculties of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait were extracted, and table (2) shows that.

Table(2)

Arithmetic means and standard deviations of faculty members' attitudes to the distance learning experience in the colleges of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait

serial	Domain	Arithmetic means	Standard Deviation	Rank	Degree
1	The quality of the training programs and technical support provided by the educational institution	4.18	0.63	1	High
2	Using Teams	4.16	0.64	2	High
3	Teaching methods through distance learning	3.62	0.85	3	Moderate
4	Student assessment through distance learning	3.31	0.91	4	Moderate
Total degree		3.81	0.65		High

It is noted from the results of Table (2) that the arithmetic means of the total degree of faculty members' attitudes to the distance learning experience in the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait was high, as the arithmetic mean reached (3.81) with a standard deviation of (0.56), and came in the first rank in the field of "quality of The training programs and technical support provided by the educational institution "with an arithmetic mean (4.18), standard deviation (0.63) and a high degree, and in the last place

came the field of “student assessment through distance learning” with arithmetic mean (3.31) and a standard deviation (0.91) and a medium degree.

The result of the study came to show that faculty members in the colleges of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training have positive attitudes towards distance education during the Corona pandemic. This result agreed with most studies that dealt with faculty members' attitudes towards distance education and e-learning in general, such as the Al-Zahrani study (2020); Al-Buhairi (2019); Shoibat (2019); monthly (2019); Saidi (2016); Muhammad (2013) and Al-Osaili (2012).

While no study was reached that differs from the current study regarding the attitudes of faculty members towards distance education, except for the study of Al-Shammari (2012), whose result did not completely differ from the current study, as the result of his study indicated the existence of moderate trends towards the use of e-learning.

The result of the current study can be justified by what was mentioned above in the commentary on previous studies, which is that the positive trends towards distance education, which were included in most studies as in the current study, indicate the presence of faculty members in the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training awareness of the importance of using technology in Teaching and perhaps its effectiveness in communicating information in line with the development in teaching methods and methods and global trends towards including technology in the educational process. Perhaps it is also that the positive attitudes of the faculty members came as a result of the conviction that formed in the international and local community that distance education is the only way to deal with the dilemma of education that was formed by the Corona crisis, which prevented students from meeting their teachers face to face, so it was necessary to use another means instead. They are staying at home and moving to the use of technology as an alternative method.

The Results of the Second Question:

To answer this question, the arithmetic averages and standard deviations of the faculty members' evaluation of the distance learning experience in the faculties of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait were extracted according to the different variables (gender, college, degree, years of experience) for the faculty member, and table (3) shows that.

Table (3)

Arithmetic means and standard deviations of faculty members' attitudes towards distance learning experience in the colleges of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait, according to gender

Domain	gender	no	Arithmetic Mean	Standard deviation
The quality of the training programs and technical support provided by the educational institution	female	83	4.30	0.60
	male	98	4.07	0.63
Using Teams	female	83	4.24	0.62
	male	98	4.09	0.66
Teaching methods through distance learning	female	83	3.74	0.83
	male	98	3.52	0.85
Student assessment through distance learning	female	83	3.33	0.93
	male	98	3.30	0.90
Total Degree	female	83	3.89	0.63
	male	98	3.74	0.66

It is noted from the results of Table (3) that there are apparent differences between the arithmetic averages, the arithmetic averages, and the standard deviations of the faculty members' attitudes towards distance learning experience in the faculties of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait, according to gender, and to find out whether these differences are statistically significant, an analysis was extracted as shown in table (7) shows this.

Table (4)

Arithmetic means, standard deviations faculty members' attitudes towards distance learning experience in the colleges of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait, according to college variable

		No	Arithmetic Means	Standard Deviation
The quality of the training programs and technical support provided by the educational institution	Basic Education	85	4.09	.64
	Technological Studies	15	4.11	.69
	Commercial Studies	40	4.18	.56
	Nursing	24	4.55	.49
	Health Sciences	17	3.59	1.03
Using Teams	Basic Education	85	4.04	.72
	Technological Studies	15	4.23	.46
	Commercial Studies	40	4.18	.50
	Nursing	24	4.58	.38
	Health Sciences	17	3.80	1.04
Teaching methods through distance learning	Basic Education	85	3.46	.83
	Technological Studies	15	3.58	.83
	Commercial Studies	40	3.64	.85
	Nursing	24	4.19	.58
	Health Sciences	17	3.40	1.39
Student assessment through distance learning	Basic Education	85	3.23	.90
	Technological Studies	15	3.21	.88
	Commercial Studies	40	3.37	.79
	Nursing	24	3.62	1.04
	Health Sciences	17	2.63	1.79
Total Degree	Basic Education	85	3.70	.66
	Technological Studies	15	3.77	.64
	Commercial Studies	40	3.83	.54
	Nursing	24	4.23	.56
	Health Sciences	17	3.35	1.32

It is noted from the results of Table (4) that there are apparent differences between the arithmetic averages, the arithmetic averages, and the standard deviations of the faculty members' attitudes to the distance learning experience in the faculties of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait according to the variable of the college, and to find out whether these differences are statistically significant, an analysis was extracted Multiple variance and Table (7) shows this.

Table (5)

Arithmetic means , standard deviations faculty members' attitudes towards distance learning experience in the colleges of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait, according to experience variable

		No	Arithmetic means	Standard Deviation
The quality of the training programs and technical support provided by the educational institution	Less than 5 Years	25	4.1689	0.60
	From 5 years to less than 10	24	4.1389	.0.64
	From 10 to less than 15	31	4.1481	.0.80
	15 years and more	101	4.1958	0.60

Using Teams	Less than 5 Years	25	4.28	0.49
	From 5 years to less than 10	24	4.08	0.71
	From 10 to less than 15	31	4.14	0.56
	15 years and more	101	4.16	0.69
Teaching methods through distance learning	Less than 5 Years	25	4.03	0.74
	From 5 years to less than 10	24	3.48	0.97
	From 10 to less than 15	31	3.42	0.74
	15 years and more	101	3.62	0.85
Student assessment through distance learning	Less than 5 Years	25	3.99	0.70
	From 5 years to less than 10	24	3.20	0.86
	From 10 to less than 15	31	3.13	0.78
	15 years and more	101	3.22	0.94
Total	Less than 5 Years	25	4.12	0.57
	From 5 years to less than 10	24	3.72	0.69
	From 10 to less than 15	31	3.70	0.58
	15 years and more	101	3.79	0.67

It is noted from the results of Table (5) that there are apparent differences between the arithmetic averages, the arithmetic averages, and the standard deviations of the faculty members' attitudes to the distance learning experience in the faculties of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait, according to the variable years of experience, and to find out whether these differences are statistically significant, it was extracted Multiple variance analysis and Table (7) show this.

Table (6)

Arithmetic means , standard deviations faculty members' attitudes towards distance learning experience in the colleges of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait, according to experience variable

		No	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation
The quality of the training programs and technical support provided by the educational institution	Lecturer	46	4.31	0.62
	Assistant Professor	67	4.30	0.61
	Associated Professor	42	3.88	0.63
	professor	24	4.10	0.57
Using Teams	Lecturer	46	4.48	0.43
	Assistant Professor	67	4.24	0.59
	Associated Professor	42	3.84	0.67
	professor	24	3.89	0.77
Teaching methods through distance learning	Lecturer	46	4.00	0.74
	Assistant Professor	67	3.76	0.79
	Associated Professor	42	3.19	0.88

	professor	24	3.25	0.74
Student assessment through distance learning	Lecturer	46	3.48	1.02
	Assistant Professor	67	3.49	0.80
	Associated Professor	42	2.96	0.91
	professor	24	3.11	0.88
Total Degree	Lecturer	46	4.06	0.61
	Assistant Professor	67	3.94	0.58
	Associated Professor	42	3.46	0.67
	professor	24	3.58	0.62

It is noticed from the results of Table (6) that there are apparent differences between the arithmetic means and the standard deviations of the faculty members' attitudes towards distance learning experience in the faculties of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait, according to the academic rank variable.

Table (7)

The results of Manova test to examine the significance of the differences between the arithmetic means of the faculty members' attitudes towards distance learning experience in the faculties of the (PAAT) according to the variables (gender, college, degree, years of experience) of the faculty members

Variance source	Dependent Variable	Sum of Square	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
gender	The quality of the training programs and technical support provided by the educational institution	.780	1	.780	2.179	.142
	Using Teams	.000	1	.000	.000	.989
	Teaching methods through distance learning	.008	1	.008	.013	.910
	Student assessment through distance learning	.793	1	.793	1.035	.311
	Total Degree	.000	1	.000	.000	.995
Faculty	The quality of the training programs and technical support provided by the educational institution	4.178	5	.836	2.332	.044
	Using Teams	2.166	5	.433	1.188	.317
	Teaching methods through distance learning	6.739	5	1.348	2.230	.054
	Student assessment through distance learning	3.528	5	.706	.921	.469
	Total Degree	3.496	5	.699	1.909	.095
Experience	The quality of the training programs and technical support provided by the educational institution	1.196	4	.299	.835	.505
	Using Teams	.695	4	.174	.477	.753
	Teaching methods through distance learning	3.607	4	.902	1.492	.207
	Student assessment through distance learning	9.777	4	2.444	3.191	.015
	Total Degree	1.466	4	.366	1.000	.409

Academic Rank	The quality of the training programs and technical support provided by the educational institution	3.348	4	.837	2.336	.058
	Using Teams	6.272	4	1.568	4.298	.002
	Teaching methods through distance learning	9.230	4	2.307	3.819	.005
	Student assessment through distance learning	2.456	4	.614	.802	.526
	Total Degree	4.548	4	1.137	3.104	.017
Error	The quality of the training programs and technical support provided by the educational institution	59.466	166	.358		
	Using Teams	60.552	166	.365		
	Teaching methods through distance learning	100.310	166	.604		
	Student assessment through distance learning	127.167	166	.766		
	Total Degree	60.807	166	.366		
Total	The quality of the training programs and technical support provided by the educational institution	3227.185	181			
	Using Teams	3208.620	181			
	Teaching methods through distance learning	2507.870	181			
	Student assessment through distance learning	2134.640	181			
	Total Degree	2702.368	181			

It is noted from the results of Table (7) that there are no statistically significant differences between the arithmetic averages of the faculty members' attitudes to the distance learning experience in the faculties of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait due to the gender variable on the total degree and all fields. The value of "P" is greater than (0.05) for each case, while the results revealed that there were statistically significant differences in the arithmetic averages of the faculty members' attitudes to the distance learning experience in the faculties of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait due to the college variable on the first domain "the quality of educational programs and technical support" while it was not. The differences are statistically significant on the other dimensions, while the results revealed that there are statistically significant differences in the arithmetic averages of the faculty members' attitudes to the distance learning experience in the faculties of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait due to the experience variable on the field of "student evaluation through distance education" While the differences were not statistically significant on the other dimensions, the results also showed that there were statistically significant differences in the arithmetic averages of the faculty members' attitudes towards The degree of distance learning in the faculties of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training in the State of Kuwait is attributed to the academic rank variable on the domains "using the Times program" and the field of "teaching methods through distance learning" while the differences were not statistically significant on the other dimensions. to find out the return of these differences, a Scheffé test was extracted for the significance of the differences and the following tables show that.

Table(8)

The results of Scheffé test for the significance of the differences between the arithmetic means for the dimension "the quality of training programs and technical support provided by the educational institution" according to college variable

		Arithmetic mean	Basic Education	Technological studies	Commercial studies	Nursing	Health Sciences
The quality of the training programs	Basic Education	4.09	-	0.03-	0.09-	0.46-*	0.50-*
	Technological Studies	4.11	-	-	0.07-	0.44-*	0.48-*

and technical support provided by the educational institution	Commercial Studies	4.18	-	-	-	0.37-*	0.41-*
	Nursing	4.55	-	-	-	-	0.04-
	Health Sciences	3.59					

It is noted from the results of Table (8) that the differences between the arithmetic mean of the dimension "the quality of training programs and technical support provided by the educational institution" are attributed to the colleges (Nursing) and (Health Sciences) when compared to other colleges.

Table(9)

The results of Scheffé test to examine the significance of the differences between the arithmetic means of the dimension of "student evaluation through distance learning" according to experience variable categories

	Experience	arithmetic mean	Less than 5 Years	From 5 years to less than 10	From 10 to less than 15	15 years and more
Student assessment through distance learning	Less than 5 Years	3.99	-	0.79*	0.86*	0.77*
	From 5 years to less than 10	3.20	-	-	0.07	0.02-
	From 10 to less than 15	3.13	-	-	-	0.09-
	15 years and more	3.22				

It is noted from the results of table (9) that the differences between the arithmetic means of the dimension of "student evaluation through distance learning" according to college variable are attributed to those with experience (less than 5 years) when compared to other categories.

Table(10)

The results of Scheffé test for the significance of the differences between the arithmetic means of the dimension of "student evaluation through distance learning" according to academic rank variable categories

	Academic Rank	Arithmetic Mean	Lecturer	Assistant Professor	Associated professor	Professor
Using Teams	lecture	4.48	-	0.24*	0.36-*	0.41-*
	Assistant Professor	4.24	-	-	0.60 *	0.65 *
	Associated Professor	3.84	-	-	-	0.05
	Professor	3.89				
Teaching methods through distance learning	Academic Rank	Arithmetic Mean	Lecturer	Assistant Professor	Associated professor	Professor
	lecture	4.00	-	0.34	0.81*	0.75
	Assistant Professor	3.76	-	-	0.57*	0.51*
	Associated Professor	3.19	-	-	-	0.06-
Total Degree	Academic Rank	Arithmetic Mean	Lecturer	Assistant Professor	Associated professor	Professor
	lecture	4.06	-	0.12	0.60	0.48
	Assistant Professor	3.94	-	-	0.48	0.36
	Associated	3.46	-	-	-	0.12-

	Professor					
	Professor	3.58	-	-	-	-

It is noted from the results of Table (10) that the differences between the arithmetic mean of the dimension of “Teams program” in different categories of the academic rank variable are attributed to those with the academic rank of “lecture” and “assistant professor” when they are compared with another academic ranks. It is also noted from the results of Table (10) that The differences between the arithmetic means on the total degree and on the field of “teaching methods through distance learning are attributed to those with the academic rank of “lecture” and “assistant professor” when compared with the other academic ranks.

First: the gender variable:

The results of the study showed no statistically significant differences between the sample members due to the gender variable. This result agreed with the results of the study of Al-Zahrani (2020); Shoibat (2019); monthly (2019); Al-Humairi (2014) and Muhammad (2013).

While no study that differs with its result from the result of the current study concerning the difference in attitudes among the study sample according to the gender variable.

Perhaps the explanation for this result lies in the fact that the Corona pandemic included all male and female faculty members and forced them to use distance education as an alternative to traditional education, which provided the opportunity to view it as a modern strategy in teaching, in addition to what we previously mentioned that awareness plays a positive role in the formation of trends, especially When it is focused on a new method of teaching (locally) and as the only and alternative option, which increases their eagerness to use it effectively and successfully to compensate for traditional education without shortcomings.

Second: The college variable

The results of the study showed that faculty members differ in their attitudes towards the distance education experience during the Corona pandemic, a difference attributed to the college variable. No study was found that (agreed with this finding. While this result differed with the study of Al-Qahtani (2010

This result, which indicated the different attitudes of faculty members towards distance education according to the faculty, can be justified by the fact that there is a discrepancy between the numbers of faculty members working in faculties. The results indicated that the faculty members working in the College of Nursing and the College of Health Sciences have positive attitudes to a greater degree than the rest of the members working in other colleges in the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training. The number of faculty members in the faculties of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training is as follows:

College of Basic Education 571 members.

College of Technological Studies 312 members.

College of Business Studies 256 members.

College of Health Sciences 81 members.

College of Nursing 81 members.

Looking at the number of faculty members working in the College of Nursing and the College of Health Sciences, it was found that their numbers are less than the number of members working in other colleges, which increases the possibility that they have sufficient devices and technologies, which increases the opportunity for them to use them. Therefore, the availability of these devices may have created a kind of connection between the faculty members in those two colleges and the use of technology, and thus this may be the reason for forming positive trends towards distance education, which of course depends entirely on computers and electronic programs.

Third: Academic Rank Variable:

The result of the study showed that there were statistically significant differences between the sample members due to the academic rank variable. This result is in agreement with the result of the Al-Shehri study (2019). While the result of the study differed with the results of the study of Al-Zahrani (2020) and Muhammad (2010).

Considering the result related to this variable; It was found that faculty members with lower academic ranks (teacher - assistant professor) had higher attitudes towards distance education than the rest of the academic ranks. This result can be attributed to the fact that the teacher and the assistant professor are considered recent college appointments or recent graduates, which means that they are more likely to use electronic devices, since most universities, especially in Western countries, rely heavily on electronic devices for teaching and obtaining information. Thus, it is likely that this is one of the reasons for forming positive attitudes towards distance education, to a greater degree than the rest of the ranks, as distance education depends on electronic devices and technologies.

Fourth: Years of Experience:

The result of the study revealed that there are statistically significant differences between faculty members according to the variable years of experience. This result agreed with the result of the study of each of Al-Shuaib (2019); monthly (2019); Al-Saeedi (2016) and Al-Shammari (2012). While the result of the current study differed with the result of the study of Muhammad (2013) and Al-Qahtani (2010).

Perhaps this result indicates that the experience factor plays a role in the formation of attitudes, as the result showed that faculty members with less than 5 years of experience had positive attitudes towards methods of evaluating students during distance education. The reason for this may be that the less experience a faculty member has in his work, the narrower his ideas about the best and effective ways of evaluating students and the need to diversify them instead of limiting them to electronic means, which may limit diversity, for example, in practical courses that require direct attendance from the student, whether To conduct laboratory experiments or practical tests in physical education. It is worth noting that there are a number of the study sample who belong to colleges that contain practical majors, such as the College of Technological Studies; College of Nursing and College of Health Sciences.

In addition; those with little experience (less than 5 years) are considered recent graduates or appointed to the faculties of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training, and therefore what we have gone to in our analysis of the reason for forming attitudes towards distance education among those with lower academic ranks applies to them. In both cases, the likelihood of them using electronic devices and technologies increases due to their recent graduation from universities, unlike those with long experiences who completed their university studies a long time ago. The more recent graduation, the greater the chances of using modern technology, and thus may give an explanation about the formation of a positive trend towards distance education due to more contact with technology .

Study Recommendations

In light of the results of the study, the researchers recommend the following:

- Intensifying training courses for teachers and overcoming the obstacles created by modern electronic programs.
- The state's work to provide an attractive environment for the use of modern educational means by providing modern equipment, fast internet, and a technical team ready to help overcome urgent problems.
- Spreading the culture of distance education through lectures and seminars for faculty members and students.
- Resuming educational and cultural activities in the faculties of the Public Authority for Applied Education and Training by transferring them electronically.

Research recommendations

- Conducting future studies of the parents' point of view on the use of e-learning for their children.
- Conducting a study to identify students' attitudes towards the distance education experience.
- Conducting a study to compare the level of students' achievement before and after the distance education experience to know its scientific impact on them.
 - Conducting a study to assess faculty members skills in using electronic technology.
 - Conducting a study to identify the best distance learning environment for both faculty members and students.

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